

From simulations to laboratory: testing the CiaoCiao wavefront sensor for phase discontinuity detection in segmented telescopes

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ABSTRACT

The next generation of extremely large telescopes will be characterized by segmented or fragmented pupils. In the case of the Extremely Large Telescope (ELT), the presence of thick spider structures supporting the secondary mirror divides the pupil into six sectors. This pupil fragmentation represents a challenge for adaptive optics (AO) systems, as conventional wavefront sensors may not correctly sense phase discontinuities across the spiders. As a consequence, the reconstructed wavefront may exhibit a so-called petalling effect, leading to a degradation of the AO correction performance. To address this issue, the “CiaoCiao Wavefront Sensor” (CiaoCiao WFS), a rotational shearing interferometer designed to measure phase discontinuities across pupil sectors, has been proposed. Previous numerical simulations using AO residual phase screens, including conditions affected by the Low Wind Effect, showed promising capabilities in retrieving differential piston between pupil regions. In this work we present the next phase of the study: the experimental validation of the CiaoCiao WFS through laboratory tests performed at the INAF – Arcetri Astrophysical Observatory. A first optical prototype was implemented using a Mach–Zehnder interferometer in which a rotated Dove prism generates the rotational shear between two replicas of the pupil. Differential piston is introduced through a custom segmented mirror mounted on a motorized linear stage. We first present measurements obtained by injecting controlled piston offsets and then discuss the integration of a deformable mirror to simulate higher-order aberrations. The results show a clear linear correlation between the injected piston and the value retrieved by the CiaoCiao WFS, demonstrating the capability of the sensor to accurately measure piston discontinuities.

Keywords: adaptive optics, wavefront sensing, piston aberration, segmented telescopes, rotational shearing interferometer, Extremely Large Telescope

1. INTRODUCTION

Adaptive optics (AO) systems play a crucial role in modern ground-based astronomy by compensating for wavefront distortions introduced by atmospheric turbulence and telescope structures. By measuring the distorted incoming wavefront in real time and correcting it through a deformable mirror (DM), AO systems enable near diffraction-limited observations. The advent of extremely large telescopes introduces new challenges for adaptive optics systems. In particular, the Extremely Large Telescope is based on a segmented primary mirror composed of 798 independent segments that must behave as a single optical surface. Maintaining phase coherence across all segments is therefore essential for achieving optimal imaging performance. Unlike monolithic mirrors, segmented pupils introduce the possibility of piston aberrations, corresponding to phase offsets between adjacent segments. In smaller telescopes piston errors are typically negligible, often smaller than the observing wavelength. However,

in extremely large telescopes they can reach amplitudes exceeding one wavelength, especially under specific conditions such as the Low Wind Effect [5]. In these cases, phase discontinuities can appear across the spider structures supporting the secondary mirror, effectively dividing the pupil into independent sectors. Conventional wavefront sensors used in adaptive optics systems are generally insensitive to such phase discontinuities. As a consequence, the reconstructed wavefront may exhibit a petalled structure, degrading the overall correction quality. To address this limitation, a dedicated sensor concept known as the CiaoCiao Wavefront Sensor (CiaoCiao WFS) has been proposed [2] [1]. The sensor is based on the principle of rotational shearing interferometry [4] and is specifically designed to measure phase differences between pupil sectors. In this work we present the first experimental validation of the CiaoCiao WFS concept through laboratory tests performed at the INAF – Arcetri Astrophysical Observatory. The goal is to evaluate the capability of the sensor to retrieve differential piston introduced between segments under controlled conditions.

2. THE CIAOCIAO WAVEFRONT SENSOR

The CiaoCiao WFS is based on the principle of rotational shearing interferometry, implemented through a Mach–Zehnder interferometer. The basic idea is to interfere two copies of the same pupil image: one unmodified and one rotated by a small angle $\Delta\theta$.

The rotation is introduced using a Dove prism placed in one arm of the interferometer. In order to maintain the same optical path length in the two interferometer arms, a second Dove prism, stationary, is placed in the other arm. This configuration ensures that both beams experience the same optical path while introducing a relative rotation between the two pupil images, as shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. Simplified Optical layout of the CiaoCiao wavefront sensor based on a Mach-Zehnder interferometer with two Dove prisms introducing a relative rotation between the beams.

As a result, each point of the pupil interferes with another point having the same radial coordinate but shifted in the azimuthal direction.

The measured signal therefore contains information on the phase difference between the two locations.

If the phase of the incoming wavefront is denoted as $\phi(r, \theta)$, the interferometer measures the phase difference

$$\Delta\phi(r) = \phi(r, \theta) - \phi(r, \theta - \Delta\theta) \quad (1)$$

where $\Delta\theta$ represents the rotation angle introduced by the Dove prism. This corresponds to the interference between two rotated copies of the pupil, as illustrated in Fig. 2.

This configuration allows the measurement of phase discontinuities between different sectors of the pupil. In the case of a segmented telescope pupil, the signal can therefore be used to retrieve the optical path difference (OPD) between adjacent segments.

The interference signal arises from the superposition of the electric fields of the two beams in the interferometer. The electric fields can be written as:

Figure 2. Conceptual illustration of rotational shearing interferometry: two copies of the same pupil are overlapped, with one rotated by a small angle $\Delta\theta$. Points with the same radial coordinate interfere while being shifted in azimuth.

$$E_1(\mathbf{r}, t) = A_1(\mathbf{r}) \cos(\omega t + \phi_1(\mathbf{r})) \quad (2)$$

$$E_2(\mathbf{r}, t) = A_2(\mathbf{r}) \cos(\omega t + \phi_2(\mathbf{r})) \quad (3)$$

The phase difference between the two beams is therefore:

$$\Delta\phi(\mathbf{r}) = \phi_1(\mathbf{r}) - \phi_2(\mathbf{r}) \quad (4)$$

and, in the case of rotational shearing, it corresponds to the phase difference between two azimuthally shifted points in the pupil.

The measured intensity at the detector is obtained from the time average of the squared sum of the two electric fields:

$$I(\mathbf{r}) = \left\langle |E_1(\mathbf{r}, t) + E_2(\mathbf{r}, t)|^2 \right\rangle_T \quad (5)$$

$$= \frac{I_1(\mathbf{r})}{2} + \frac{I_2(\mathbf{r})}{2} + \sqrt{I_1(\mathbf{r})I_2(\mathbf{r})} \cos(\Delta\phi(\mathbf{r})) \quad (6)$$

Finally, the phase difference can be directly related to the optical path difference (OPD) through:

$$\text{OPD} = \frac{\lambda}{2\pi} \Delta\phi \quad (7)$$

3. LABORATORY IMPLEMENTATION

3.1 Optical bench setup

The CiaoCiao WFS was implemented on an optical bench at the laboratories of the INAF – Arcetri Astrophysical Observatory in Florence, Italy. As a light source we used a He–Ne laser operating at a wavelength of 632.8 nm. The beam interact with a deformable mirror the ALPAO88 and interact with a Pistonator (see 3.2) and after is injected into a Mach–Zehnder interferometer where it is split into two arms. In one of the two arms a Dove prism is used to introduce the rotational shear between the two pupil images (see the theory behind in 2). The two beams are then recombined to produce interference fringes on the detector, carrying information about the phase difference between rotated points of the pupil (see Figure 3).

3.2 Piston injection system

To simulate piston aberrations between segments, we developed a custom device referred to as the pistonator (Figure 4). The pistonator consists of a segmented mirror obtained by cutting a flat mirror into two halves. One of the halves is mounted on a motorized linear stage (PI N-565), allowing controlled displacements along the optical axis. By moving the stage with nanometric precision, it is possible to introduce a controlled optical path difference between the two mirror halves. The system allows displacements with a precision of approximately 3 nm. The segmented mirror is placed upstream of the interferometer so that the injected piston can be measured by the CiaoCiao WFS.

Figure 3. Photograph of the CiaoCiao WFS experimental setup on the optical bench at the Adaptive Optics Laboratory of the Arcetri Astrophysical Observatory. The optical path starts from the laser source, is reflected by the ALPAO DM88 deformable mirror, propagates through the pistonator for controlled phase injection, and enters the CiaoCiao WFS, after the interferogram is finally recorded by the camera.

Figure 4. Photo of the pistonator as implemented on the actual CiaoCiao optical bench. The image shows the two halves of the segmented mirror: the right half is mounted on a fixed base, while the left half is mounted on the motorized linear stage (PI N-565), allowing precise piston displacements along the optical axis.

Figure 5. Fourier-transform phase reconstruction pipeline based on the method of Takeda et al. (a) Raw interferogram acquired by the camera. (b) Interferogram after application of a spatial mask to restrict the analysis to the pupil region. (c) Logarithmic magnitude of the Fourier spectrum, showing the central DC component (zero-frequency term) and the two symmetric sidebands introduced by the spatial carrier. (d) Fourier spectrum after spatial filtering: one of the sidebands is isolated using a Gaussian band-pass filter, while the DC component and the conjugate term are suppressed and the selected lobe is shifted to the origin. (e) Wrapped phase map obtained from the reconstructed complex field using the atan2 function. (f) Same phase map after application of the spatial mask.

4. PHASE RECONSTRUCTION AND DATA ANALYSIS

The phase reconstruction is performed using a Fourier-transform fringe analysis approach applied to interferograms containing a spatial carrier, following the Fourier-transform method originally introduced by Takeda et al. [6] and implemented according to the formulation described in [3]. This technique enables phase retrieval from a single interferogram and is particularly suitable in the presence of environmental perturbations or dynamic conditions where phase-shifting methods are not applicable.

The different stages of the reconstruction process are illustrated in Fig. 5.

The interferogram recorded by the camera can be modeled as

$$I(x, y) = A(x, y) + B(x, y) \cos[\phi(x, y) + 2\pi(f_x x + f_y y)], \quad (8)$$

where $A(x, y)$ represents the background intensity (DC component), $B(x, y)$ is the fringe modulation amplitude, $\phi(x, y)$ is the phase difference between the two interferometer arms, and (f_x, f_y) are the spatial carrier frequencies introduced by the tilt between the beams.

The presence of the spatial carrier shifts the phase-related spectral components away from the origin in the Fourier domain, allowing their separation from the DC component through spatial filtering. The reconstruction procedure consists of the following steps.

First, the interferogram is acquired by the camera (Fig. 5a) and a spatial mask is applied to isolate the pupil region (Fig. 5b). The masked interferogram is then transformed into the frequency domain using a two-dimensional Fourier transform (Fig. 5c), where the DC component and the two symmetric sidebands can be clearly identified.

A Gaussian band-pass filter is used to isolate one of the sidebands containing the phase information. The selected spectral component is shifted to the origin of the Fourier domain to remove the spatial carrier (Fig. 5d). The filtered spectrum is then transformed back to the spatial domain through an inverse Fourier transform, yielding a complex analytic field I_f from which the phase information is retrieved. The wrapped phase map is obtained by computing the arctangent of the ratio between the imaginary and real parts of this field (Fig. 5e):

$$\phi_w(x, y) = \text{atan2}(\Im\{I_f(x, y)\}, \Re\{I_f(x, y)\}) \quad (9)$$

This operation provides the wrapped phase in the interval $[-\pi, \pi]$. The spatial mask is then reapplied to restrict the phase estimation to the pupil region and suppress residual background contributions (Fig. 5f). Finally, phase unwrapping on each pupil sector is performed when a continuous phase distribution is required.

The optical path difference (OPD) is obtained from the reconstructed phase as

$$\text{OPD}(x, y) = \frac{\lambda}{2\pi} \phi_w(x, y) \quad (10)$$

To estimate the piston aberration, the OPD is averaged over predefined sectors of the pupil mask. This approach relies on the assumption that the phase within each sector is dominated by the piston term intentionally introduced by the pistonator, while higher-order aberrations and atmospheric turbulence introduce only minor spatial variations. Under these conditions, the OPD can be considered approximately uniform within each sector, and the mean value provides a robust estimate of the piston. This assumption is justified by the controlled laboratory conditions and the limited spatial extent of each sector.

For each sector, the mean OPD is computed and wrapped to the measurement wavelength, producing a time series of piston estimates. For the current configuration, where the segmented mirror consists of two segments with a relative rotation of 120° , four overlapping pupil sectors are defined, as illustrated in Fig. 6.

Figure 6. Geometrical representation of the overlap between two copies of the same pupil in the current configuration of the CIAO-CIAO WFS. The second copy is rotated by 120° , producing four distinct overlap regions. Points with the same radial coordinate interfere while being shifted in azimuth.

Two sectors correspond to cross-interference between different segments (1-2 and 2-1), yielding piston values of equal magnitude and opposite sign. The remaining two sectors (1-1 and 2-2) correspond to self-interference and therefore yield zero piston, as expected.

This approach provides a robust and efficient method for piston estimation in segmented optical systems using a single interferogram. The accuracy of the piston estimation depends on the quality of the spatial filtering and the separation between the spectral components in the Fourier domain.

5. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

5.1 Experimental Results: Temporal Stability at Zero Piston Command

The temporal stability of the measurement system has been assessed under static conditions, i.e., with the piston command set to zero. The experimental setup used for this analysis is the one described in Section 3.1. In this configuration, the Pistonator was actuated only once at the beginning of the acquisition sequence to define the initial position, and subsequently kept fixed for the entire duration of the measurement.

A sequence of 300 consecutive frames was acquired, each with an exposure time of 10 ms. This dataset enables a time-resolved characterization of the piston measurement under nominally stable conditions, providing a direct estimate of the intrinsic noise and temporal stability of the system.

To remove any static offset, the piston value measured in the first frame was taken as a reference and subtracted from all subsequent measurements. This normalization allows the analysis to focus on relative fluctuations, independently of the absolute initial position of the stage.

Figure 7 shows the measured piston as a function of the frame index for the two analyzed sectors (left and right), as defined in Section 4. The two time series exhibit a clear anti-correlation: when one increases, the other decreases.

This behavior is expected from the measurement principle. In the right sector the piston is computed using the 2-1 sectors combination, while in the left sector the combination 1-2 is used. As a consequence, the retrieved piston values are expected to have equal magnitude and opposite sign in the two sectors. The observed opposite trends therefore confirm the internal consistency of the measurement and indicate that the fluctuations are not purely random, but are at least partially driven by a common underlying variation (e.g. instrumental or environmental).

A statistical analysis of the data yields the following results:

- Left sector: mean = 5.11 nm, standard deviation = 4.92 nm
- Right sector: mean = -7.13 nm, standard deviation = 4.48 nm

The standard deviation, of the order of ~ 5 nm for both sectors, provides a direct estimate of the short-term measurement stability.

The small non-zero mean values are primarily related to the normalization procedure, which uses the first frame as a reference. This makes the mean sensitive to noise or bias in the initial measurement, as well as to possible slow drifts over time. For this reason, the standard deviation is considered a more reliable metric of the short-term stability than the mean value.

Overall, these results indicate that the system achieves nanometric-level stability under static conditions and that the measurement is consistent across the two sectors.

Figure 7. Measured piston as a function of time (frame index) under zero piston command. The left (blue) and right (orange) sectors are shown separately. Dashed lines indicate the mean values for each sector.

5.2 Experimental Results: Piston ramp

The results shown in Fig. 8 were obtained by physically moving the pistonator in discrete steps of 10 nm, starting from the initial reference position up to a maximum displacement of approximately 80 nm. After each step, 10 images were acquired, each with an exposure time of 5 ms. The use of multiple frames per step allows for averaging, improving the statistical robustness of the estimated piston and reducing the impact of measurement noise.

Figure 8. Measured piston position as a function of the true piston displacement for the left and right sectors, together with linear fits, and the corresponding residuals.

The analysis is performed separately for two sectors, referred to as the left and right sectors. For each sector, the measured piston displacement is plotted against the true (commanded) displacement, together with a linear fit. The fitted slopes slightly deviate from the ideal values (approximately -1.014 for the left sector and 1.046 for the right sector). This indicates a small scaling mismatch between the commanded mechanical displacement and the measured optical response.

In our reflective configuration, the piston is introduced by displacing one of the two segments of the Pistonator (Fig. 4). A mirror displacement Δx generates a wavefront optical path difference (OPD) of $2\Delta x$ between the perturbed and reference wavefronts, due to the round-trip propagation upon reflection. Accordingly, a 10 nm displacement results in a 20 nm variation of the reflected wavefront, and the measured signal directly corresponds to twice the physical displacement.

Taking into account that the two sectors correspond to opposite optical path differences ($2-1$ and $1-2$), the measured slopes are expected to have the same magnitude and opposite sign, consistently with the anti-correlated behavior observed in the zero-piston analysis. Within this framework, the measured slopes are consistent with the expected interferometric response within a few percent.

The residuals, shown in the right-hand panels of Fig. 8, represent the difference between the experimental data and the corresponding linear fits. Ideally, residuals should be randomly distributed around zero without any systematic trend. In this case, the residuals remain within a few nanometers, indicating a good agreement with the linear model. A weak structure is nevertheless visible, suggesting the presence of minor systematic effects rather than purely random noise. These may arise from non-linearities in the system response or environmental perturbations.

Overall, the results confirm a linear and monotonic response of the sensor to piston variations over the explored range, with a scaling factor consistent with the expected interferometric behavior.

The piston ramp was restricted to a sub- $\lambda/2$ range to prevent phase wrapping, ensuring a unique phase-to-OPD mapping and enabling a consistent linear characterization of the sensor response.

6. FUTURE DEVELOPMENTS

As a next step, the ALPAO DM88 deformable mirror will be used to introduce residual aberrations that reproduce those generated by an adaptive optics system on extremely large telescopes, such as the ELT. The goal is to extend the validation from pure piston conditions to a more realistic regime where piston is combined with higher-order aberrations.

The main objective is to evaluate the robustness of the piston estimation in the presence of spatially varying phase distortions, representative of residual wavefront errors delivered by an adaptive optics system on telescopes such as the Extremely Large Telescope.

Future work will focus on:

- assessing the sensitivity of the sensor to higher-order aberrations in addition to piston,
- evaluating its performance under residual turbulence conditions,
- extending the current setup to broadband illumination.

These developments are necessary to assess the performance of the sensor under conditions representative of real telescope operation.

7. CONCLUSION

We have presented a laboratory characterization of the CiaoCiao wavefront sensor for the measurement of piston discontinuities in a segmented pupil, based on a Mach–Zehnder interferometric implementation with spatial carrier and Fourier-transform phase retrieval.

The experimental validation was carried out through two complementary tests addressing temporal stability and response linearity. Under static conditions (zero piston command), the system exhibits a temporal stability of approximately 5 nm RMS over a sequence of 300 frames acquired in about 60s. This value provides a direct estimate of the short-term measurement noise and demonstrates nanometric-level repeatability in the absence of commanded perturbations. The observed anti-correlated behavior between the two analyzed sectors further confirms the internal consistency of the reconstruction method, as expected from the definition of the two sector combinations.

The piston ramp measurements show a clear linear response of the sensor over a sub- $\lambda/2$ range, with measured slopes close to the expected interferometric scaling. The two sectors exhibit slopes of opposite sign, as anticipated from the underlying measurement geometry, and agree with each other within a few percent when accounting for the expected symmetry. Residuals with respect to the linear fits remain confined to a few nanometers and do not reveal dominant systematic trends, although small deviations from ideal linearity are present and can be attributed to a combination of normalization effects, experimental uncertainties, minor systematic contributions, and environmental fluctuations.

Overall, these results demonstrate that the proposed sensing approach provides a consistent and repeatable measurement of piston under controlled laboratory conditions, with nanometric stability and a well-behaved linear response within the explored range.

Future work will extend this validation to more realistic scenarios by introducing higher-order aberrations using a deformable mirror and by assessing the robustness of the piston retrieval in the presence of spatially varying wavefront errors. Additional investigations will also address performance under conditions closer to on-sky operation, including residual turbulence and broadband illumination. These steps are required to fully assess the applicability of the method to segmented telescope systems such as those of extremely large telescopes.

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